

DIPHENYL (PIPERIDIN-4-YL) METHANOL DERIVATIVES AS POTENTIAL CANDIDATES FOR ANTIFUNGAL AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITIES: SYNTHESIS, SPECTRAL CHARACTERIZATION, AND *IN-VITRO* STUDY

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Abstract

WHO has declared Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) as one of the top global public health and developmental threats. The rising challenge of multidrug resistance (MDR) underscores the urgent need for novel antimicrobial agents to combat infections. In this study, we explored the chemistry of Diphenyl(piperidin-4-yl)methanol (DPP) and its substituted molecules within a unified molecular framework by synthesizing six new derivatives through the alkylation of the piperidine nitrogen of DPP with various phenacyl halides. The structures of these derivatives were elucidated using EIMS, ¹H-NMR, UV, and FTIR techniques. Agar well disc diffusion method was used to evaluate the antibacterial and antifungal activities of synthesized compounds. Antibacterial assay showed significant zones of inhibition (ZOI ≥ 12 mm) against various bacterial strains. Notably, 4NP and DCP were highly effective against *Proteus mirabilis*, which causes urinary tract infections and related complications. 4NP also demonstrated significant activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Enterobacter*. DCP was notably effective against *Shigella dysenteriae*, responsible for shigellosis. In antifungal assays, 3NP, 4NP, DHP, and DCP surpassed fluconazole in ZOI against various fungal strains. 3NP showed superior inhibition against *Candida albicans*, indicating potential for treating candidiasis. DCP was effective against *Penicillium* spp., suggesting potential for treating penicilliosis. 4NP was the most potent, particularly against *Aspergillus niger*, with a ZOI of 25 mm, nearly

double that of fluconazole. SAR analysis indicated that nitro and hydroxyl substitutions enhanced inhibition potential, especially at the para position. The study concludes that the lead molecule DPP and its derivatives, especially 4NP and DCP, exhibit promising antibacterial and antifungal activities, making them potential candidates for treating various infections. Further optimization and in vivo studies are recommended to realize their clinical potential fully.

Keywords: Synthesis, Piperidine, Structure Elucidation, Antibacterial, Antifungal.

1. INTRODUCTION

The relationship between humans and infectious bacterial pathogens dates back to antiquity (1). In 2019 alone, bacterial infections accounted for 7.7 million deaths worldwide, highlighting the ongoing global health challenge posed by antimicrobial resistance (2). Despite efforts in pharmaceutical science, the development of new antibacterial drugs has slowed, exacerbating the issue of resistance among pathogens like *S. aureus* and *S. pneumoniae* (3, 4). Multidrug-resistant bacteria, particularly Gram-negative strains, further complicate treatment outcomes and mortality rates (5, 6). Secondary bacterial, fungal, or viral pulmonary infections and co-infections have emerged as common and severe complications of COVID-19. Research indicates that although the generally rate of these infections in COVID-19 patients is generally low, it is notably high among those in Intensive Care Units (ICUs), correlating with poorer clinical outcomes (7). Reports suggest that secondary bacterial infections were involved in 50% of COVID-19 fatalities(8) Additionally, multiple studies have shown that over 90% of patients having these diseases received empirical antibiotics, thereby increasing the risk of multi-drug-resistant (MDR) infections (9, 10)

Similarly, fungal infections pose significant threats, ranging from superficial to systemic diseases(11). Opportunistic yeasts like *Candida* spp. are prominent causes of mucosal and systemic infections, particularly in immune-compromised patients (12). The persistence of invasive fungal infections, coupled with emerging resistance to antifungal agents, underscores their impact on global health, with mortality rates ranging from 20% to nearly 100% depending on the infecting organism (13, 14). In response to these challenges, ongoing research into new antibacterial and antifungal agents is crucial to combating resistance and improving treatment outcomes worldwide.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 General experimental conditions

All chemicals, including DPP, were sourced from Sigma Aldrich Company, and analytical grade solvents were used throughout the experiments. Filtration was performed using Wattman's filter paper. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) plates, Kieselgel 60 (GF-254), were employed for monitoring reaction and to check purity of synthesized compounds. The synthesized compounds' spots were visualized under ultraviolet light at 254 or 365 nm using an HP-UVIS Desaga (Heidelberg). The compounds were desiccated. Melting points were determined using a Buchi 434 apparatus. UV spectra were recorded with a

Hitachi U-3200 spectrophotometer, using methanol as the solvent. FT-IR spectra were obtained with a Jasco 302 Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer using the KBR disc method. Mass spectrometry was conducted using Varian Mass Spectrometers MAT 113, MAT 311 A, MAT 312, and DMASPEC systems. ¹H-NMR spectral analysis was performed on a Bruker AM 300, 400 spectrophotometer.

2.2 Method of Synthesis:

Diphenyl (piperidin-4-yl) methanol (DPP) derivatives 1–6 were synthesized via nucleophilic substitution reactions with various alkylating agents through N-alkylation. The synthesis process involved refluxing DPP with different phenacyl halides in acetone in a round-bottom flask. The reaction solution was vigorously stirred magnetically and heated to 75°C for 48–72 hours. The progress of reaction was monitored using thin-layer chromatography (TLC). Upon completion, the solid products were filtered and washed with acetone. Purification was achieved through recrystallization using dichloromethane or warm ethanol. The purified products were then dried in desiccators containing anhydrous silica gel beads (15). The melting points of the pure compounds were recorded and are uncorrected.

2.3 Protocol of antibacterial and antifungal activity:

These assays were conducted using the disc diffusion method. Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar were prepared and autoclaved for antibacterial and antifungal testing, respectively. The sterilized media were poured into Petri dishes and allowed to solidify. Bacterial and fungal cultures were prepared by inoculating nutrient broth with the tested strains and incubating at 37°C for day. The turbidity of strain suspensions was standardized against a McFarland standard to ensure uniform concentration. (16). Bacterial or fungal suspensions were swabbed onto agar plates, ensuring even distribution by rotating the plate at a 60° angle. Sterile filter paper discs (6 mm diameter), impregnated with the test compounds dissolved in DMSO at 10 mg/mL, were placed on the agar surface. Petri dishes were then at 37°C incubated for a day. Antibacterial and antifungal activity was evaluated by measuring zones of inhibition in millimeters around the discs. A zone of inhibition ≥12 mm was considered significant. Negative controls included DMSO, while Amphotericin B and fluconazole served as standards for antibacterial and antifungal activity, respectively. (17, 18).

2.4 Synthesis Basics:

The synthesized compounds were categorized into three main regions labeled as 1, 2, and 3, as depicted in synthetic scheme 1:

1. A Lead molecule Diphenyl(piperidin-4-yl)methanol [DPP].
2. Linker Region (connecting the piperidine ring with the terminal ring system).
3. Terminal phenyl Ring System (Phenyl ring with varying substitutions at the meta and para positions).

Table 1: provides detailed information on the chemical structures of each reaction's spacer region (R) and terminal (X), as outlined in the scheme.

SYNTHETIC SCHEME-1

Table 1: Detail of Linker and Terminal Ring(R)

COMPOUND CODE	SPACER/LINKER	TERMINAL RING/R
1-BRP		
2-4NP		
3-3NP		
4-DHP		
5-3FP		
6-DCP		

2.5 Physicochemical Characterization:

1. 1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-(4-(hydroxydiphenylmethyl)piperidin-1-yl)ethan-1-one [BRP]

2. 2-(4-(hydroxydiphenylmethyl)piperidin-1-yl)-1-(3-nitrophenyl)ethan-1-one [3NP]:

3. 2-(4-(hydroxydiphenylmethyl)piperidin-1-yl)-1-(4-nitrophenyl)ethan-1-one [4NP]

4. 1-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-2-(4-(hydroxydiphenylmethyl)piperidin-1-yl)ethan-1-one[DHP]

White crystalline solid with a molecular formula of C₂₆H₂₇NO₄ and a molecular weight of 417.49 a.m.u. The compound has a melting point of 287 ±2°C. The ¹H-NMR (DMSO, 400 MHz) spectrum shows δ(ppm): 8.509 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 8.132 (s, 2H, Ar-H), 7.510-7.493 (t, J=6.8 Hz, 4H, Ar-H), 7.293-7.262 (t, J=12.4 Hz, 4H, Ar-H), 7.157-7.128 (t, J=11.6 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 5.595 (s, 1H, H-11), 3.328 (s, 2H, H-7), 3.254-3.230 (m, 2H, H-3a, H-5a), 2.887-2.841 (m, 2H, H-3b, H-5b), 2.072 (m, 1H, H-4), 1.628-1.542 (m, 2H, H-2a, H-6a), 1.599-1.416 (d, 2H, H-2a, H-6b). EIMS m/z (relative intensity, %): 417.5 (M⁺). UV λ_{max} (MeOH) nm: 262.8 and 216.6. IR u_{max} (KBr) cm⁻¹: 3406.29, 3128.54, 2780.44, 1643.35, 1245.41, 1111.0.

5. 2-(4-(hydroxydiphenylmethyl)piperidin-1-yl)-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)ethan-1-one [3FP]

White crystalline solid with a molecular formula of C₂₆H₂₇F₃NO₂ and a molecular weight of 453.46 a.m.u. The compound has a melting point of 270 ±2°C. The ¹H-NMR (DMSO, 400 MHz) spectrum shows δ(ppm): 8.4590 (s, 2H, Ar-H), 8.1174 (s, 2H, Ar-H), 7.5164-7.4979 (d, J=7.4 Hz, 4H, Ar-H), 7.3089-7.2704 (t, J=15.4 Hz, 4H, Ar-H), 7.1731-7.1367 (t, J=14.5 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 5.6049 (s, 1H, H-11), 3.3301 (s, 2H, H-7), 2.8889-2.8315 (m, 2H, H-2a, H-6a), 2.5047-2.4959 (t, J=3.52 Hz, 2H, H-2b, H-6b), 2.0837 (s, 1H, H-4), 1.6088-1.5462 (t, J=7.70 Hz, 2H, H-3a, H-5a), 1.4323-1.3981 (d, 2H, H-3b, H-5b). UV λ_{max} (MeOH) nm: 319.00, 255.00, and 204.00. FTIR u_{max} (KBr) cm⁻¹: 3429.43, 3132.4, 2787.14, 1639.49, 1246.02, 1016. EIMS m/z (relative intensity, %): 453.5 (M⁺)

6. 1-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)-2-(4-(hydroxydiphenylmethyl)piperidin-1-yl)ethan-1-one [DCP]

White crystalline solid with a molecular formula of C₂₆H₂₅Cl₂NO₂ and a molecular weight of 454.39 a.m.u. The melting point is 286 ±2°C. The ¹H-NMR (DMSO, 400 MHz) spectrum shows δ(ppm): 8.46-8.12 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 7.52-7.50 (d, J=7.99 Hz, 4H, Ar-H), 7.31-7.17 (t, J=12.33 Hz, 4H, Ar-H), 7.15-7.14 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 5.60 (s, 1H, H-11), 3.27-3.24 (d, 4H, H-7, H-2a, H-6a), 2.94-2.86 (d, 2H, H-2b, H-6b), 2.03 (s, 1H, H-4), 1.64-1.54 (m, 2H, H-3a, H-5a), 1.43-1.40 (d, 2H, H-3b, H-5b). UV λ_{max} (MeOH) nm: 257.80, 253.00, and 207.40. FTIR u_{max} (KBr) cm⁻¹: 3429.43, 3126.61, 2787.14, 1625.99, 1244.09. EIMS m/z (relative intensity, %): 454.4 (M⁺).

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The antibacterial evaluation as represented in Table 2, revealed that the lead molecule DPP and its derivatives BRP, 4NP, DHP, and DCP except 3NP and 3FP showed significant zones of inhibition (ZOI) against various bacterial strains, with a ZOI of 12 mm or greater considered significant. Structural activity relationship (SAR) analysis indicated

that modifications at the terminal phenyl ring affected antibacterial potency. 4NP and DCP were particularly effective against *Proteus mirabilis*, with 4NP emerging as the most potent inhibitor. *Proteus mirabilis* is known to cause urinary tract infections (UTIs) and can lead to complications such as kidney stones and sepsis. The nitro group at the para position (4NP) significantly enhanced activity against *S. aureus* and *Enterobacter*. Substitutions with hydroxyl and chlorine groups at Meta and para positions of both DHP and DCP compound respectively resulted in significant activity against *E. coli*. Halogen substitutions (bromine and fluorine) rendered the compounds inactive against most strains, except DCP, which maintained activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *S. epidermidis*. DCP was notable for its significant activity more than amphotericin B (ZOI 15mm) against *Shigella dysenteriae* (zoi 18mm) suggesting its potential for treating shigellosis, a disease that causes severe diarrhea, abdominal pain, and fever.

The antifungal evaluation as shown in Table 3, demonstrated that 3NP, 4NP, DHP, and DCP surpassed the standard antifungal drug fluconazole in ZOI against various fungal strains. 3NP showed superior inhibition against *Candida albicans*, suggesting its potential for treating candidiasis. DCP exhibited significant activity against *Penicillium spp.*, indicating its potential for treating penicilliosis. 4NP was the most potent inhibitor against all tested strains, particularly against *Aspergillus niger*, with a ZOI of 25 mm, almost double that of fluconazole. SAR analysis for antifungal activity highlighted that nitro and hydroxyl substitutions enhanced inhibition potential, particularly when the nitro group was at the para position. Halogen substitutions generally reduced antifungal activity, except for *Candida albicans*. The position of the functional groups significantly impacted inhibition potential.

Table 2: Antibacterial activity by agar well diffusion method (Zone of inhibition in mm)

S/No	Organisms	DPP	BRP	3NP	4NP	DHP	3FP	DCP	Amphotericin B
1	<i>E.coli</i>	10	-	-	-	12	-	14	25
2	<i>S. aureus</i>	12	-	-	15	-	-	12	18
3	<i>Shigella dysenteriae</i>	-	-	-	14	-	-	18	15
4	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	10	-	-	14	12	10	13	28
5	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	14	11	10	15	10	10	14	15
6	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	10	-	-	-	-	-	10	15
7	<i>S.epidermidis</i>	12	10	11	11	11	10	12	25
8	<i>Streptococcus spp</i>	-	12	-	12	-	-	10	24

Where,

– : no activity

Amphotericin B: positive control

Table 3: antifungal activity by agar well diffusion method (Zone of inhibition in mm)

S/No.	Organisms	DPP (Lead)	BRP	3NP	4NP	DHP	3FP	DCP	Fluconazole
1	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	-	-	-	25	-	-	-	15
2	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	-	-	-	16	-	-	-	10
3	<i>Candida albicans</i>	12	10	15	15	15	10	11	13
4	<i>Rhizomucor pusillus?</i>	-	10	-	19	-	-	-	11
5	<i>Penicillium spp.</i>	-	11	-	14	-	-	14	10
6	<i>Candida spp.</i>	11	-	14	13	19	15	-	25

Where,

– : no activity

Amphotericin B: positive control

4. CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the lead molecule DPP and its derivatives, particularly 4NP and DCP, exhibit promising antibacterial and antifungal activities. 4NP emerged as a potent inhibitor against both bacterial and fungal strains, making it a potential candidate for treating a range of infections, including candidiasis, aspergillosis, and bacterial infections caused by *Proteus mirabilis*, which can lead to urinary tract infections and related complications. DCP demonstrated significant activity against *Shigella dysenteriae*, which causes shigellosis, and *Penicillium spp.*, highlighting its potential for treating severe diarrhea and penicilliosis. The SAR analysis underscored the importance of specific functional groups and their positions in enhancing antimicrobial potency. These findings provide a strong foundation for future optimization and development of novel therapeutic agents with improved efficacy and reduced resistance profiles. Further studies focusing on in vivo pharmacokinetics and therapeutic applications are recommended to fully realize the clinical potential of these compounds.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflict of interest.

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